

Model Predictive Control for Disruption-aware Supply Chain Networks

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Abstract: The development of global manufacturing centers has shifted industry focus toward building efficient and reliable supply chain networks composed of decentralized processing layers along the manufacturing pipeline. To benefit from this transition, it is important to deliberately account for dynamic demands, unpredictable disruptions in the capabilities of the processing layers, and also accommodate the diverse customer requirements expressed as high-level intents. This paper introduces an intent-based Model Predictive Control framework to optimize the scheduling of admissible flows between the Supply Chain Network, considering also fluctuating customer demands and the production rates of each processing node. The framework is compared against other baseline approaches, and the evaluation results indicate significant benefits by providing at least 39% reduction in the overall cost.

Keywords: Model Predictive Control, Control and Optimization of Supply Chains, Supply Chain Network, Flow Networks, Manufacturing as a Service

1. INTRODUCTION

Optimal management of supply chains entails the design and operation of a Supply Chain Network (SCN). To achieve efficiency and timely delivery while adhering to environmental sustainability goals (Abualigah et al. (2023)), SCNs require managing trade-offs between cost, resource usage, and delivery performance across different suppliers, production sites, and distribution channels. The management of SCNs remains challenging as it requires solving complex decision-making problems related to supplier selection, production planning, transportation logistics, and distribution (Menon and Ravi (2022)). Also, the planning and scheduling of supply chains within multi-supplier and multi-factory networks should efficiently adapt to time-varying customer demands and heterogeneous requirements, ensuring that customer's needs are met in a timely and resource-efficient manner (Almaktoom et al. (2014)).

Customer requests often require coordinated efforts across multiple production sites, where intermediate assets or

elements are produced and distributed before the final production stage. This leads to a sequential and distributed execution of production tasks across distinct sites (Lohmer and Lasch (2021)). Additional complexity arises from the diverse configurations of upstream supply SCNs, where multiple manufacturers, arranged either in parallel or in series, contribute to the production process (Almaktoom et al. (2014)). These introduce varying structural constraints, interdependencies, and coordination challenges that significantly impact scheduling, resource allocation, and overall system performance (Wang et al. (2023)).

The shift of the manufacturing industry towards the Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) paradigm promises to enable modularity of production planning and delivery operations and on-demand services, opposed to traditional, fixed-structure supply chain management approaches (Li et al. (2023)). This is further accelerated by the emergence of servitization, where industries extend their production capabilities by offering services or resources to external customers on a temporary or on-demand basis (Sharma and Singh (2017)). Moreover, customer orders have different requirements, which can be expressed as high-level intents, that need to be accommodated by the SCN man-

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agement. Enabled by digital technologies, these paradigms will support modular service composition and dynamic orchestration of manufacturing resources, allowing SCNs to flexibly adapt and respond to various customer intents.

However, the shift from static, predetermined production flows to dynamic, modular manufacturing networks enabled by the emergence of MaaS and servitization raises several challenges. These include efficiently orchestrating production processes in real time, deciding which resources to engage, allocating service-level demands, and sequencing tasks across diverse providers with varying capabilities and conditions (Lohmer and Lasch (2021)). Ensuring that distributed production paths satisfy both customer intents (e.g., on-time delivery, cost) and system-level objectives (e.g., efficiency, robustness) adds significant complexity. To tackle this, various optimization models have been proposed. For instance, a MILP approach jointly coordinates suppliers, production, distribution, and demand, adapting plans dynamically through a rolling horizon (Perea-López et al. (2003)). Likewise, Mixed Logical Dynamical systems have been used to capture discrete switching in multi-product, multiechelon supply chains, enabling centralized Model Predictive Control (MPC) for maximizing value (Mestan et al. (2006)). Several other methods address these challenges through different control schemes and optimization techniques (Eskandarpour et al. (2015)), but often fall short of fully capturing the real-time variability or supporting truly adaptive orchestration capabilities.

In this paper, a predictive, intent-aware framework based on MPC principles is introduced for optimization of dynamic supply chain network operations. The proposed framework is designed to coordinate sequential-constrained production processes undertaken by distributed production sites, which are structured in multiple process-specific supply chain layers. The main contributions are:

- The modeling of SCN as sequentially constrained processes, represented by a directed labeled graph, along with the dynamic description of the SCN state evolution.
- The introduction of a set of admission nodes, equipped with buffers, into the SCN graph to manage customer demand flows, enabling flexible dispatching of flows across the network, in contrast with (Almaktoom et al. (2014)).
- The formulation of a time-horizon-based SCN optimization problem, and the design of an MPC-based framework that incorporates uncertainties concerning customer demand and service rates, and leverages updated state and information to adaptively solve the optimization problem.
- The demonstration of the effectiveness of the proposed framework compared to alternative baseline strategies by providing simulation-based evaluation results, validating improvements in operational performance.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows. In Section 2, the proposed SCN modeling is presented along with its dynamics and constraints. Section 3 introduces the MPC approach. Finally, in Section 4, the evaluation is presented, and Section 5 provides conclusions and discusses possible future directions.

2. SYSTEM MODELING

Vector inequalities hold componentwise. The set of non-negative reals and integers is denoted by \mathbb{R}_+ and \mathbb{N}_+ respectively. For a vector, possibly with a subscript $x_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we write $x_{k,i}$ to denote its i -th component. The vector with elements equal to one is denoted by $\mathbf{1}$.

2.1 SCN and customer request parameters

Let the directed graph $G = (V, E)$ represent the SCN, where a set of different customer demands/intents $\{1, \dots, C\}$ is submitted. The set of nodes V is organized into layers indexed from 0 to $M + 1$, with $V = \{V_0, V_1, \dots, V_M, V_{M+1}\}$. Each node v is labeled by the pair (i, j) , meaning the i^{th} node at layer j , where $j \in \{0, \dots, M + 1\}$ and $i \in \{1, \dots, N_j\}$, with N_j being the number of nodes at layer j . Layer 0 corresponds to the admission nodes that regulate the inflow of customer demands into the SCN, while the layer $M + 1$ represents the sink nodes associated with delivered customer flow. The graph G is assumed to be pairwise bipartite, meaning that edges exist only between nodes in consecutive layers. The set of directed labeled edges is

$$E = \{(s, d, \sigma) \mid s \in V, d \in V, \sigma \in \Sigma\}.$$

The edge labels, and thus the set Σ , are vector signals corresponding to the admissible routed demand flows at time t , i.e.,

$$\Sigma = \{u_{(s,d)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^C \mid s \in V_j, d \in V_{j+1}, j \in \{0, \dots, M\}\}.$$

The c -th element of the vector $u_{(s,d)}(t)$, denoted by $u_{(s,d),c}(t)$, corresponds to the flow routed through the edge (s, d) for the customer c at time t .

For each node, we define the sets of ingoing and outgoing flow vectors. Thus, for a node $d \in V$ the set of ingoing flow vectors is

$$I(d) = \{u \in \Sigma : (\exists s \in V : (s, d, u) \in E)\},$$

while for a node $s \in V$, the set of outgoing flow vectors is

$$O(s) = \{u \in \Sigma : (\exists d \in V : (s, d, u) \in E)\}.$$

Considering the management of flow within the processing nodes, each node $v \in V$ maintains a buffer vector $z_v(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^C$, capturing the queued demand at node $v \in \{V_0, \dots, V_M\}$. The element $z_{v,c}(t)$ corresponds to the buffer state at node $v = (i, j)$ for customer c at time t . We consider the vector $\mathbf{z}(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\mathcal{N}}$, to be the concatenation, e.g., using lexicographic ordering, of the buffer state vectors for each node v of the graph, with $\mathcal{N} = C \sum_{j=0}^M N_j$. Similarly, we denote with $\mathbf{q}(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\mathcal{M}}$ the vector concatenation of processing rates of production site nodes of the SCN, where $\mathcal{M} = C \sum_{j=1}^M N_j$. Element $q_v(t)$ of $\mathbf{q}(t)$ denotes the processing rate of $v \in \{V_1, \dots, V_M\}$.

To represent the dynamic demand placed on the SCN, we define the customer request parameters over time as follows. Let $r(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^C$ denote the vector of discrete customer request demands at time t , with its c -th element $r_c(t)$ being the demand flow from customer c . In our scheduling modeling framework, we consider the customer demand flow is submitted first to a buffer at the layer $j = 0$. In this layer, each node $(i, 0)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, is responsible for dispatching orders to the first production

Fig. 1. SCN model with M processing layers, the admission nodes at layer 0 and the system output at layer $M + 1$ (at left), alongside with the buffer state, processing rate and flow decision variables of a node $v = (i, j)$ (at right).

layer nodes $(i, 1)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, N_1\}$. These admission nodes extend the graphical structure of G , introducing another layer of $N_0 = C$ nodes used as sources of flow and do not process demands themselves. Although existence of buffers that do not process demand may seem counterintuitive, it can provide an advantage in the overall decision problem, e.g., (Spatharakis et al. (2022)).

To incorporate intent-based preferences regarding the logistic routing of customer demands, we introduce a quantification of these preferences. Thus we define the customer intent vector at time t as:

$$\xi(t) = [\xi_1(t) \dots \xi_C(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{N}^C.$$

The intent of each customer $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ is represented by a value $\xi_c(t) \in \mathbb{N}$, capturing qualitative preferences related to the routing of the demanded flow within the supply chain network. For example, these intents may reflect the customers' environmental and sustainability considerations and can express preference for the routing, favoring paths that involve low-emission links.

2.2 System Dynamics

The introduction of the buffer states allows the manufacturing process to be modeled as a dynamical system, in contrast to typical approaches in flow networks, e.g., Bertsekas (1991). This captures how customer demand propagates through the SCN and impacts the buffering behavior at each node, both per customer and in total. Considering the production site nodes $v = (i, j) \in V$, for $j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ and $i \in \{1, \dots, N_j\}$, the buffer state vector update is

$$z_v(t+1) = z_v(t) + \sum_{u(t) \in \mathcal{I}(v)} u(t) - \sum_{u(t) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} u(t). \quad (1)$$

The update for the nodes of the first layer $v = (i, 0)$, related to the customer i for all $i \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, is

$$z_v(t+1) = z_v(t) + r_i(t) - \sum_{u(t) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} u(t). \quad (2)$$

The system outputs are the production rates for each customer of the SCN and can be computed based on the outgoing flow of the last production layer M . Let $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^C$ represent the total final product demand flow routed to all customers at time t . The output value for each customer $y_c(t)$, $c = 1, \dots, C$, is

$$y_c(t) = \sum_{s \in V_M} \sum_{u(t) \in \mathcal{O}(s)} u_c(t), \quad (3)$$

where $u_c(t)$ is the c -th element of the vector $u(t)$. In essence, $y_c(t)$ is the label of the nodes within the last layer of the SCN (Fig. 1), where each node collects the respective flows of customer $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$.

2.3 System Constraints

We introduce a set of constraints related to the processing capabilities and routing decisions at each node in the SCN.

First, we impose a *service rate capacity* on each node: the total routed flow leaving a node at any time must not exceed its processing capacity. In particular, for each node $v \in V$, the following holds

$$\sum_{u(t) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} 1^\top u(t) \leq q_v(t). \quad (4)$$

The buffer states across all nodes are non-negative, ensuring that the system does not process or route negative quantities of demand, i.e.,

$$z_v(t) \geq 0, \quad v \in V. \quad (5)$$

A structural constraint applies specifically to the initial input layer, i.e., when $j = 0$, where each $v = (i, 0)$ corresponds to a single customer $c = i$. Thus, only the respective buffer's c -th element, i.e. $z_{v,c}(t)$, may take nonzero values

$$z_{v,c}(t) = 0, \quad i \neq c. \quad (6)$$

At the final production layer M , the SCN must ensure that each outgoing edge from any node $s \in V_M$ routes flow exclusively for the relate customer. Specifically, for any edge $(s, d) \in E$ where $d = (i, M + 1)$ corresponds to customer i , the flow for customer c should be zero unless $c = i$. This can be modeled as:

$$u_{(s, d), c}(t) = 0, \quad \forall s \in V_M, \quad d = (i, M + 1), \quad c \neq i. \quad (7)$$

Finally, the total fulfilled demand $y_c(t)$ for each customer c must not exceed the requested amount $r_c(t)$ submitted at time t , i.e.,

$$y_c(t) \leq r_c(t), \quad (8)$$

for all $c = 1, \dots, C$. We remark that this constraint leads to storing excess flow within the SCN state buffers. As we will observe in the subsequent section, since the system design does not impose an upper bound on buffer capacities but instead penalizes large buffer sizes, this constraint does not introduce infeasibility into the model, and at the same time captures a realistic specification.

3. MPC-BASED SCN OPTIMIZATION

This section presents the formulation of the optimization problem for SCN operations, followed by the development of an MPC-based framework for its solution. The proposed framework optimizes SCN performance over a finite prediction horizon H , by repeatedly solving the formulated optimization problem based on the current system state and forecasts of future demands and processing rates.

3.1 Objective Function

Let $J_F(t)$ denote the deviation of demand fulfillment considering all the customers at time t , where

$$J_F(t) = \mathbf{1}^\top |y(t) - r(t)|. \quad (9)$$

To incorporate intent-based costs, we associate each edge of the SCN with a weight that reflects the cost of utilizing a particular path. This cost represents the level of alignment between the routing characteristics and the customer expressed intent. Let

$$\mathcal{L} = \{l_e \in \mathbb{N} \mid e \in E\},$$

be the set of such weights. Thus, for each edge $(s, d, \sigma) \in E$, the weight $l_{(s,d)} \in \mathbb{N}$ is assigned to distinguish preference to an intent between the production sites $s \in V_j$ and $d \in V_{j+1}$, for $j \in \{1, \dots, M-1\}$. This formalism allows to generate scheduling and resource allocation strategies taking explicitly into account the possibly time-varying customer intent $\xi(t)$. To this purpose, and for each customer demand $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, we define the intent deviation or drift from the preferred $\xi_c(t)$ at time t and for an edge $e = (s, d, u(t))$ as $\delta_{e,c}(t)$, where

$$\delta_{e,c}(t) = u_c(t) |\xi_c(t) - l_e|. \quad (10)$$

The vector $\delta_{(s,d)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^C$, represents the deviation of intent label for an edge (s, d) , where $s \in V_j, d \in V_{j+1}, j = 0, \dots, M-1$, for all customers. Thus, the cost related to intent deviation for all customers within every edge of the SCN at time t is calculated as follows:

$$J_{\text{In}}(t) = \sum_{e \in E} \mathbf{1}^\top \delta_e(t). \quad (11)$$

Furthermore, let $J_B(t)$ denote the penalty associated with the buffer usage across all nodes at time t . This penalty is calculated as the maximum absolute buffer load across all nodes in the SCN at time t , where

$$J_B(t) = \|\mathbf{z}(t)\|_\infty. \quad (12)$$

3.2 Customer Demand and Processing Rates Estimation

SCN optimization requires forecasts of the future customer demands and the processing rates of each production site over a prediction horizon. Thus, the vectors $r(t)$ and $\mathbf{q}(t)$ should be estimated for future time steps. To this end, a Holt linear exponential smoothing method is adopted to capture the temporal trends of $r(t)$ and $q(t)$. For each customer demand component $r_c(t)$, $c = 1, \dots, C$, and each processing rate for each node $q_v(t)$, $v \in V$, the one-step ahead estimation is calculated as follows:

$$\tilde{r}_c(t) = \hat{r}_c(t) + \gamma_c^r(t), \quad (13)$$

$$\tilde{q}_v(t) = \hat{q}_v(t) + \gamma_v^q(t), \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{r}_c(t)$ and $\hat{q}_v(t)$ denote the smoothed estimates for the customer demand and processing rates, respectively, $\gamma_c^r(t)$ and $\gamma_v^q(t)$ represent the estimated linear trends.

The smoothing and trend update equations at each time step are defined separately for customer demand and for processing rates as follows:

$$\hat{r}_c(t) = \alpha_r r_c(t) + (1 - \alpha_r)(\hat{r}_c(t-1) + \gamma_c^r(t-1)), \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma_c^r(t) = \beta_r(\hat{r}_c(t) - \hat{r}_c(t-1)) + (1 - \beta_r)\gamma_c^r(t-1), \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{q}_v(t) = \alpha_q q_v(t) + (1 - \alpha_q)(\hat{q}_v(t-1) + \gamma_v^q(t-1)), \quad (17)$$

$$\gamma_v^q(t) = \beta_q(\hat{q}_v(t) - \hat{q}_v(t-1)) + (1 - \beta_q)\gamma_v^q(t-1), \quad (18)$$

where $\alpha_r, \beta_r, \alpha_q, \beta_q \in (0, 1)$ are smoothing constants controlling the adaptation of demand and processing values. The prediction is used recursively, acknowledging a progressive increase in uncertainty. The values $\hat{r}_c(0)$, $\gamma_{r,c}(0)$ and $\hat{q}_v(0)$, $\gamma_{q,v}(0)$ are initialized based on historical averages and zero initial trends, respectively. The h -step ahead estimations are calculated using (13), (14), multiplying the linear trends by h . Regarding the intent of each customer $\xi_c(t)$, in this work, its value is assumed to be known and externally specified for every time step t within the prediction horizon.

3.3 Optimization cost and MPC problem formulation

The objective concerns the minimization of the cumulative cost within the finite time horizon H . Given an initial time t_0 and an initial state of buffers $\mathbf{z}_0 = \mathbf{z}(t_0)$, we define the set of admissible control decisions as $\mathcal{U} = \cup_{\tau=0}^{H-1} \mathcal{U}_\tau$ where the collection of all admissible flow decision variables at time step τ is:

$$\mathcal{U}_\tau = \{u(\tau) \mid (\exists s \in V, d \in V : (s, d, u(\tau)) \in E)\}.$$

The total cost $J(\mathbf{z}_0, \mathcal{U})$ is given by:

$$J(\mathbf{z}_0, \mathcal{U}) = \sum_{\tau=0}^{H-1} (w_1 J_F(\tau) + w_2 J_{\text{In}}(\tau) + w_3 J_B(\tau)), \quad (19)$$

where the weights w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 are scalars that control the relative importance of the flow deviation, intent deviation, and buffer penalty costs, respectively. Thus, the optimization problem Ψ is formulated as follows

$$\Psi : \min_{\mathcal{U}} J(\mathbf{z}_0, \mathcal{U}) \quad (20)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{z}_0 = \mathbf{z}(t) \quad (20a)$$

$$u_{(s,d)}(\tau) \geq 0, \forall (s, d, u) \in E, \tau = 0, \dots, H-1, \quad (20b)$$

$$z_v(\tau) \geq 0, \forall v \in V, \tau = 1, \dots, H, \quad (20c)$$

$$y(\tau) \leq \tilde{r}(\tau), \tau = 1, \dots, H, \quad (20d)$$

$$\tilde{q}_v(\tau) \geq \sum_{u(\tau) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} \mathbf{1}^\top u(\tau), \forall v \in V_j, \quad (20e)$$

$$j = 1, \dots, M, \tau = 1, \dots, H-1,$$

$$z_v(\tau+1) = z_v(\tau) + \sum_{u(\tau) \in \mathcal{I}(v)} u(\tau) \quad (20f)$$

$$- \sum_{u(\tau) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} u(\tau), v \in V_j, j = 1, \dots, M,$$

$$z_v(\tau+1) = z_v(\tau) + \tilde{r}(\tau) \quad (20g)$$

$$- \sum_{u(\tau) \in \mathcal{O}(v)} u(\tau), v \in V_0, \tau = 1, \dots, H-1.$$

The problem Ψ is solved at each time instant t , and subsequently the optimal values of the flow vectors in

Fig. 2. Normalized Cumulative Cost J over H .

\mathcal{U}_0^* are applied in the receding horizon fashion see, e.g., Rawlings et al. (2017). We note the optimal values of the flow vectors for the subsequent steps of the control horizon, as well as the estimate of the demand the service rate, are discarded and recalculated at the next time instant.

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS AND EVALUATION

This section presents the simulation-based performance evaluation of the proposed MPC-based framework, detailing the experimental setup and evaluation methodology.

4.1 Experiment Setting and Evaluation Metrics

The simulation framework was implemented in Python, and Gurobi Optimizer was the selected solver¹. The considered SCN follows the work of (Almaktoom et al. (2014)), with the corresponding system parameters defined as follows. The network comprises $M = 4$ production layers, each containing $N_j = 5$ production sites $j \in [1, M]$. The number of customers is $C = 5$, and the number of production sites and logistics routes between them was arbitrarily selected. Also, we selected to include three levels of intents, i.e., $\xi_c(t), l_{(s,d)} \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, $\forall s \in V_j, d \in V_{j+1}, j = [1, M - 1]$. The customer request demands and the processing rates of the production site nodes fall within the ranges (20, 60) and (30, 60), respectively, with the processing rate at each node equally allocated among all customers. Finally, the optimization horizon equals $H = 20$, while the admissible flows were selected for $T = 60$ time steps. All results are averaged over 10 runs.

The proposed framework is compared against three baseline methods, namely (a) Static optimization- no buffers (SOPT-NB), (b) Static optimization with Buffers (SOPT-B), and (c) MPC-no buffers (MPC-NB). Specifically, for *SOPT-NB* and *MPC-NB*, we selected to evaluate the importance of including buffers in the first layer of the SCN. Similarly, we compare against the two Static solutions, which solve the optimization problem (20) only once at the beginning of each horizon H , without updating decisions based on the evolving system state and updated forecasts. Besides the cost defined in (19), the following evaluation metrics are also defined. The total intent cost to flow delivery ratio denoted by $\lambda(t)$ is defined as:

Fig. 3. Total Intent Cost to Flow Delivery ratio over H .

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{J_{\text{In}}(t)}{1^\top y(t)}, \quad (21)$$

Note that $\lambda(t)$ is not part of the optimization objective but is used as an evaluation metric to assess the trade-off between intent deviation cost and actual system's service rate. Such trade-offs are commonly used in SCN studies (Camacho-Vallejo et al. (2023)).

$$K_1 = \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} J_{\text{In}}(t), \quad (22)$$

denoting the total intent deviation cost over the time horizon H . The metric K_2 :

$$K_2 = \left(\sum_{j=1}^M N_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \sum_{v \in \{V_1 \dots V_M\}} 1^\top z_v(t), \quad (23)$$

denotes the average buffer state over all nodes summed for the entire time horizon H . Finally, the evaluation metric K_3 is defined as follows:

$$K_3 = (CH)^{-1} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{y_c(t)}{r_c(t)}. \quad (24)$$

Therefore, K_3 denotes the average value of the delivered flow to the demand ratio over the time horizon H . It is worth noting that $r_c(t) > 0 \quad \forall t \in T$.

4.2 MPC-based Framework Evaluation Results

In Fig. 2, cumulative costs are normalized by the maximum final cost across all methods for fair, scale-independent comparison. It is observed that the proposed MPC-B method significantly outperforms the baseline approaches. Static methods, particularly SOPT-NB, exhibit higher cumulative costs as a result of a lack of foresight, failing to anticipate future demand and processing variations, leading to inefficient decisions over time. Lower performance is remarked also for the methods without admission layer buffers (i.e., SOPT-NB and MPC-NB), highlighting the importance of admission layer buffers that alleviate flow pressure on the following production layers. Among these, SOPT-NB performs the worst due to both its static nature and its lack of admission layer buffering capability. Overall, the MPC-B framework achieves at least a 39% reduction in cumulative cost over the optimization horizon $H = 20$ compared to the next-best method (MPC-NB), and significantly outperforms both static baselines,

¹ <https://www.gurobi.com/solutions/gurobi-optimizer/>

Table 1. Evaluation Metrics K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 .

Method / Metric	K_1	K_2	K_3
MPC-B	1683	80	0.93
MPC-NB	2433	1534	0.95
SOPT-B	1700	128	0.90
SOPT-NB	2038	1980	0.91

indicating efficient balancing of intent alignment, buffer utilization, and delivery accuracy.

The second experiment (Fig. 3) examines the time evolution of the cumulative average of the intent deviation-to-delivery ratio, $\lambda(t)$. Again, MPC-B consistently achieves superior performance with the lowest $\lambda(t)$ values across the horizon. This indicates that our proposed framework delivers high volumes of flow with minimal intent violation cost, demonstrating efficient alignment with customer preferences. Conversely, non-buffered methods admit the total initial customer demands directly into production layers, which lack the flexibility to absorb demand fluctuations, leading to higher $\lambda(t)$ values. The higher cumulative $\lambda(t)$ value observed for MPC-NB compared to SOPT-NB stems from the fact that λ is a derived evaluation metric and not directly optimized. A key factor contributing to this behavior is that MPC-NB optimizes the buffer occupancy term $\|\mathbf{z}(t)\|_\infty$ in the cost function, lacking the ability to regulate input flow. In the absence of the admission layer, the MPC-NB strategy prioritizes minimizing the maximum buffer load by routing flows through less-preferred paths, leading to higher intent deviation and thus higher λ . This trade-off is directly influenced by the selected weights (w_1, w_2, w_3). In contrast, SOPT-NB, although suboptimal, is not constrained by receding-horizon feedback and may unintentionally achieve a lower cumulative λ due to its static optimization strategy.

Table 1 presents a quantitative comparison between the assessed methods using the evaluation metrics K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 . The MPC-B achieves the lowest total intent deviation cost, indicating its effectiveness in aligning flow routing with customer intents throughout H . Compared to MPC-B, the intent deviation cost increases by approximately 45% in MPC-NB, 1% in SOPT-B, and 21% in SOPT-NB. Additionally, MPC-B exhibits the lowest average buffer usage, demonstrating the importance of the admission layer buffers' inclusion. Compared to MPC-B, all alternative methods result in higher buffer usage. The flow delivery efficiency of MPC-B, is comparable to other methods, reflecting a balanced performance in satisfying customer demands while minimizing intent violations and excessive buffer utilization. Although MPC-NB achieves a slightly higher flow delivery ratio, it falls short at balancing the intent deviation cost and buffer burden, with significantly higher values in both metrics. Similarly, SOPT-B outperforms SOPT-NB in both K_1 and K_2 , benefiting from buffer inclusion. However, their inability to adapt to temporal dynamics, results in suboptimal performance compared to MPC-based strategies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an MPC-based framework for SCN management considering dynamic processing rates for the production sites and service demands. The framework

optimizes the total cost of the SCN and minimizes the divergence of the required customer intents. Specifically, the proposed solution achieves at least 39% reduction in total cost compared to other baseline solutions. Regarding our future plans, we aim to extend the proposed modelling and also incorporate control-theoretic approaches to provide robust, cost-, and energy-optimized solutions for the challenging problem of controlling the processing rates.

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